

A novel method to measure the relative strong phase between $D^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 \pi^+ \pi^-$ and $\bar{D}^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 \pi^+ \pi^-$ amplitudes

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Abstract

We present a novel method to measure the relative phase between D^0 and \bar{D}^0 in the self-conjugate final state of $K_S^0 \pi^+ \pi^-$. This method is then applied to the measurements of the CKM angle γ measured from $B^\pm \rightarrow D(\rightarrow K_S^0 \pi^+ \pi^-) K^\pm$ decays. We refer to this method as the ‘quasi model independent’ method (or QMI method) which has similar statistical precision to the unbinned model dependent method in measurements of γ , which offers the greatest precision in γ measurements from this channel, but avoids incurring systematic uncertainties due to mismodelling of the relative phase between D^0 and \bar{D}^0 .

Ultimate precision in γ The angle, $\gamma \equiv \text{Arg}\left(\frac{V_{cd}V_{cb}^*}{V_{ud}V_{ub}^*}\right)$ (or ϕ_3) is the angle of the ‘unitarity triangle’ that occurs from requiring that Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa (CKM) matrix V_{ij} is unitary, $V_{ud}V_{ub}^* + V_{cd}V_{cb}^* + V_{td}V_{tb}^* = 0$. It is the only angle that has no terms involving the top quark elements of the CKM matrix. The angle γ can be determined through tree level processes involving $b \rightarrow c$ transitions. These tree level measurements have an ultimate relative theoretical error of $\frac{\delta\gamma}{\gamma} \sim 10^{-7}$ [1] after which one must account for loop contributions. By contrast, the world average precision on γ is $\gamma = (65.9_{-3.5}^{+3.3})^\circ$ [2], i.e. orders of magnitude larger than this theoretical limit to precision at tree level. The most precise measurements of γ are obtained from decays of B^\pm to D^0 (or \bar{D}^0) and K^\pm with the neutral charm meson decaying to a self-conjugate multi body final state such as $K_S^0\pi^+\pi^-$, known as the BPGGSZ method [3]. Currently, the measurement of γ via these final states is limited by the available statistics of B^\pm decays. By the time of the end of the proposed ‘upgrade II’ of the LHCb experiment [4], a data sample corresponding to 300 fb^{-1} of pp collisions will be obtained, approximately 30 times the amount collected currently. In addition to this, the Belle II [5] experiment will be competing with LHCb to measure γ using data samples produced in e^+e^- collisions. With this increase in sample size, it is expected that the statistical precision in γ measurements will be below 1° . At such statistical precision, the impact of systematic uncertainties on γ will become larger.

Model dependent method The most statistically optimal way to obtain γ from $B^\pm \rightarrow D(\rightarrow K_S^0\pi^+\pi^-)K^\pm$ decays is by constraining γ (along with r_B and δ_B) via maximising an unbinned likelihood for $B^\pm \rightarrow D(\rightarrow K_S^0\pi^+\pi^-)K^\pm$ decays. To do this, one uses an amplitude model for $D^0 \rightarrow K_S^0\pi^+\pi^-$ decays, obtained from the B factories such as Belle [6] and BaBar [7], which have $\mathcal{O}(10^7)$ events to constrain an amplitude model. In model dependent (MD) methods, one must then account for systematic uncertainties due to the choice of model one uses for $D^0 \rightarrow K_S^0\pi^+\pi^-$ decays.

Model independent method If one instead splits the $K_S^0\pi^+\pi^-$ phase-space into bins and constrains $\Delta\delta_D(s_+, s_-)$ via the amplitude averaged cosine and sine of $\Delta\delta_D$, c_i and s_i using data from quantum correlated $D^0\bar{D}^0$ produced at the $\psi(3770)$ resonance at the BESIII detector [8], one can obtain a model independent (MI) measurement of $\Delta\delta_D$. This MI measurement can then be fed into a binned measurement of γ from $B^\pm \rightarrow D(\rightarrow K_S^0\pi^+\pi^-)K^\pm$ decays at LHCb. The penalty for this model independence is a reduction of sensitivity to γ due to binning the $K_S^0\pi^+\pi^-$ phase-space. In addition to this, the statistical uncertainties on c_i and s_i become systematic uncertainties in measurements of γ .

The QMI method We propose a method [9] that attempts to avoid the systematic uncertainties associated with mismodelling $\Delta\delta_D$ by adding a correcting polynomial to the $\Delta\delta_D$ obtained from a particular model, $\Delta\delta_D(s_+, s_-) \rightarrow \Delta\delta_D(s_+, s_-) + f(s_+, s_-|C)$, with C being the free parameters used to shape the two-dimensional polynomial. We assume no CP violation in the $D^0 \rightarrow K_S^0\pi^+\pi^-$ decay, which means that the relative strong phase $\Delta\delta_D(s_+, s_-) = -\Delta\delta_D(s_-, s_+)$. This means that the correcting polynomial must also satisfy $f(s_+, s_-) = -f(s_-, s_+)$. We therefore construct the correcting polynomial as: $f(s_+, s_-) = \sum_i \sum_j C_{i,2j+1} p_i(s_+ + s_-) p_{2j+1}(s_+ - s_-)$ where C_{ij} are free parameters, and $p_i(x)$ are one dimensional polynomials of order i . This method assumes that the magnitudes $|A^{D^0}(s_+, s_-)|$ are accurate and that the uncertainties in these magnitudes are negligible compared to those in $\Delta\delta_D$.

Study of effect of mismodelling $\Delta\delta_D$ on γ In figure (1), we show the pull distributions of the pull parameters of $x_\pm, y_\pm = r_B(\cos(\delta_B \pm \gamma), \sin(\delta_B \pm \gamma))$, $\text{pull}(x) \equiv \frac{x - x^{\text{Gen}}}{\sigma_x}$. The pull parameter measures the difference between the measured value of a parameter x compared to the true (or generated) value, x^{Gen} normalised to the reported error σ_x . If each pseudo-experiment is independent of each other (in this case, we simulate the samples used in each pseudo-experiment with a

Figure 1: The pull distributions $\text{pull}(x) \equiv \frac{x - x^{\text{Gen}}}{\sigma_x}$ of $x_{\pm}, y_{\pm} = r_B(\cos(\delta_B \pm \gamma), \sin(\delta_B - \gamma))$ from $N = 100$ independent pseudo-experiments where we apply a bias to the relative strong phase $\Delta\delta_D$. The black bars correspond to $\langle \text{pull} \rangle \pm \frac{s(\text{pull})}{\sqrt{N}}$ (in the centre) and $(\langle \text{pull} \rangle - s(\text{pull})) \pm \frac{s(\text{pull})}{\sqrt{2N}}$ (at the edges), where $s(x) = \sqrt{\langle x^2 \rangle - \langle x \rangle^2}$.

different seed for the random number generator) then the distribution of the pull distributions of x_{\pm}, y_{\pm} should follow a normal distribution with central value μ and width σ . We generate $N = 100$ samples from $\psi(3770) \rightarrow D^0 \bar{D}^0$ and $B^{\pm} \rightarrow D(\rightarrow K_S^0 \pi^+ \pi^-) K^{\pm}$ decays using the model for $D^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 \pi^+ \pi^-$ decays obtained by the combined analysis from the Belle and BaBar experiments [10]. To test if our method can compensate from mismodelling the relative strong phase, we apply a bias to $\Delta\delta_D$ and examine if our correcting polynomial can recover the true $\Delta\delta_D$. We modify $\Delta\delta_D$ with a two-dimensional function $f_{\text{bias}}(s_+, s_-) = A \cdot \text{erf}\left(\frac{s_- - s_+}{\varepsilon}\right) G(s_- - s_+, \mu_-, \sigma_-) \cdot G(s_+ + s_-, \mu_+, \sigma_+)$, where we set $\mu_+ = 2.5$, $\mu_- = 1.0$, $\sigma_{\pm} = 1$, $\varepsilon = 0.1$, $A = 1$ and $G(x, \mu, \sigma)$ is a one dimensional Gaussian distribution.

Statistical precision in γ The statistical precision in γ obtained from the two standard methods (the unbinned MD method and binned MI method) are shown alongside our unbinned QMI method in figure (2). We show $\langle \gamma \rangle \pm \langle \sigma_{\gamma} \rangle$, the average-measured value of $\gamma \pm$ the average of the reported uncertainty in γ from $N = 100$ statistically independent pseudo-experiments (similar to the pull distributions shown in figure (1), except no bias is applied to $\Delta\delta_D$). We observe that for both the MD and QMI methods, the precision in γ is similar and the MI method has a larger statistical uncertainty. This is consistent with the MI method losing precision due to binning the $K_S^0 \pi^+ \pi^-$ phasespace.

Conclusion We have shown the development of the QMI method to measure γ from $B^{\pm} \rightarrow D(\rightarrow K_S^0 \pi^+ \pi^-) K^{\pm}$ decays. We have used simulated $\psi(3770)$ and B^{\pm} decays to determine the

Figure 2: The distribution of γ from $N = 100$ independent pseudo-experiments, using the MD, QMI and MI methods to obtain γ .

relative precision in γ from the unbinned MD and binned MI methods, as well as our novel method. We also show the results of pull studies for the novel method. We show that the QMI method has similar statistical power as the MD method and is able to ‘recover’ the $\Delta\delta_D$ using a simulated bias to the relative strong phase.

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